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The Individual Patterns of Learning – The Indicators of Vocational Teachers' Professional Development and Quitting the Profession

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Abstract

This study considers how the learning patterns of vocational teachers relate to their career decision-making process. As a starting point, vocational teachers' careers involve a high level of occupational mobility. Therefore, vocational teachers have made career-related decisions related to previous studies or followed new perspectives and opportunities. According to Krumboltz's learning theory of career decision-making process, a person considers experiences which are gained through direct or indirect learning while choosing a career or studying path. Drawing on an analysis of narrative interviews with 24 vocational teachers and two previous vocational teachers, the article analyses the influence of learning experiences on becoming a vocational teacher.

Keywords

direct learning; indirect learning; vocational teachers' career; transferable skills

1 Introduction

One of the challenges for many educational systems is a question on how to recruit and keep vocational teachers who have pedagogical and practical skills and knowledge of the workplace (OECD, 2014). To solve the vocational teachers' shortage the strategy to encourage practitioners to enter vocational teaching has been launched on policy level (OECD, 2010). At the same time, the attractiveness of the vocational teacher's profession is affected by low salary levels (Misra, 2011) and lack of social recognition (Grollmann, 2008). Yet, work satisfaction may be related to personally meaningful work (Rosso et al., 2010). However, there is little known about the reasons explaining why individuals choose the vocational teachers work and how their learning patterns are connected to life career. The viewpoints of the vocational teachers' career decision-making and related learning might give an explanation about aspects, which are important in terms of recruitment and professional development of vocational teachers.

The career path of vocational teachers may involve a rather high level of occupational mobility. The fact that vocational teachers have a background in an initial occupation (Andersson et al., 2018) offers to them several career prospects on the labour market. As the skills and individual competencies acquired during the former career remain valuable, there are no

barriers when switching back to the former occupation after working at vocational school. The return to former occupation still bears the risk that pedagogical skills acquired during teaching may not be congruent with the further occupational career. Although vocational teachers are sometimes considered as “low skilled” in academic terms (Andersson & Köpsén, 2015) they possess specific skills and know-how, acquired during the occupational and educational path.

Qualification requirements for vocational teachers vary by country. In most countries tertiary education is required as entry level, in some countries (the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Iceland, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Spain) a master degree is required (Cedefop, 2016). However, considering the mobility in the vocational teacher’s career path is not sufficient to confine learning narrowly by the academy or by the workplace. Instead, learning is a continuous life-long process that occurs in all contexts in which individuals have been lived (Allix, 2011). Personal histories determine individual identities and the way they engage in work and exercise their agency (Billett, 2011). Although in the identity construction process, individuals are active agents (Vähäsantanen & Billett, 2008), the colleagues play a significant part, as individual claims of belonging must be accepted by others (May, 2013). Also, individual and shared values are shaped and re-shaped by the social context of work (Beckett & Hager, 2002). Socialisation, involved mainly in informal learning, broadens the awareness of colleagues and opens the door to tacit knowledge and therefore a more effective way of job performance (e.g. Eraut, 2011). In the negative line, workplace learning might lead to the realization that this is not a satisfying organisation to work for (Beckett & Hager, 2002).

As learning occurs everywhere and in each situation, vocational teachers learn from their own experience, from colleagues, from students. Also, feedback, messages from family or societal attitude towards vocational education have to be considered as indirect learning experiences. The association of these messages with occupation produces a positive or negative response, which will be relevant in future career decision-making (Patton & McMahon, 2014). To support vocational teacher’s recruitment and workplace motivation, it’s necessary to understand the patterns of individual learning in career decision-making.

2 Theoretical framework

In the centre of Krumboltz’s learning theory in the career decision-making process (1979) is the idea that individuals acquire their career predilections through the learning experiences. It is important to recognize that individual educational and occupational decision-making is influenced in a large extent by factors usually outside the control of the individual (Krumboltz et al., 1976). Krumboltz distinguishes four categories of factors which influence an individual’s career decision-making process: genetic endowment and special abilities; environmental conditions and events; learning experiences and task approach skills. It is not essential to know exactly what portion of the variance is due to genetic or environmental influencers, but it should be recognized that individuals are born with greater or lesser predispositions to profit from a certain type of learning experiences (Krumboltz et al., 1976).

In the present study, we are mainly focusing on the two types of learning experiences: direct, instrumental, and indirect, associative. Direct learning experiences are those in which the individual acts on the environment to produce certain consequences, which include the direct effects produced by the action (feedback) and the observable result of the action itself (Krumboltz, et al., 1976). The direct learning type involves genetic endowments and environmental conditions. Through these experiences, an individual learns skills relevant to decision-making about careers which in their view is appropriate to them (Patton & McMahon, 2014). The term indirect learning refers to the development of positive and negative attitudes and beliefs about occupations through a broad array of external stimuli (e.g. positive or negative message about occupation). Thus, indirect learning refers to an individual reaction to external

stimuli (Krumboltz, et al., 1976), which will be relevant in career decision-making (Patton & McMahon, 2014).

In this paper we are asking:

1. Which learning patterns (direct and indirect learning) experienced during the lifespan have influenced the vocational teacher's career?
2. How has learning during the vocational teacher's career increased individual competencies and transferable skills?
3. Which direct or indirect learning aspects have increased or decreased vocational teacher's professional stability?

2.1 Expected outcomes

We assume, that becoming a vocational teacher and keeping hold of teachers' occupation is related to positive interaction between direct and indirect learning. Secondly, we suggest, that learning which has been taken place during vocational teacher's career supported the development of the transferable skills, and thus an individual's better perspectives in the labour market.

3 Methodology

The research is based on narrative life history interviews, which is suitable to find out the impact and influence of past events and individuals experiences (Bold, 2012). Altogether 24 vocational teachers and two former vocational teachers were interviewed. The youngest interviewee was 24-years old and the oldest 67-years old. The interviews with former vocational teachers aimed to gain information about the reasons for quitting and the perceived importance of gained skills for the further career path. The average length of the interview was one and a half hours. Analysing the transcribed interviews, we applied the tree-steps thematic analysis (Ryan & Bernard, 2003). First, we coded content units. Then we aggregated the content units into categories and categories into themes.

4 Results

From the narratives collected from the vocational teachers, the following themes, explaining their learning and career decision-making process emerged: 1) the genetic endowment and childhood environment; 2) the aspects and outcomes of direct learning; 3) the outcomes of indirect learning; 4) task approach and suitability of vocational teachers work; 5) transferable skills.

4.1 Genetic endowment and childhood environment

Vocational teachers do not bring out any specific abilities while speaking about their childhoods. However, some loved singing, others preferred acting or sports. Several interviewees characterized themselves as leaders, good communicators or performers.

While speaking about home and parents, interviewees mentioned they are from a "*simple family*" or "*my parents were regular workers*". Some had parents with an academic degree but there was also vocational teacher, whose father had only 6-grades of education. Remarkably, many interviewees had grown up with grandparents or foster parents. Regardless of the family type, childhood home influenced life values, behavioural norms, workplace habits. Some noted that parent (mum, father, grandfather) has been his/her greatest teacher. In several cases, people had taken the parent's vocation as a model. For example, people chose the chef's profession after stepmom. Others followed their relatives who seemed to have a seemingly profitable job.

All relatives whom I associated with have usually been studying sort of functional knowledge, so there are few theoreticians and many kinds of hands-on workers. And this is influencing a lot. (Aivar, 45)

The first career decision was made after graduating from compulsory school. Some chose the academic path and continued studies in high school, others went to a vocational school. The choices made after compulsory school were mostly influenced by the socio-economic context. Those who chose vocational school wanted to acquire skills which would ensure quick access to the labour market. Some considered personal characteristics like communicativeness or individual need for autonomy. For example, one of the interviewees explained that the need for independence made him choose electrician's profession. Decision-making was also influenced by a previous connection to a certain occupation. Vocational teachers who had chosen an academic path did not consider vocational education as an option, mainly due to the bad reputation of vocational education, which they had indirectly learnt from attitudes made by teachers or parents.

Taken together genetic and environmental components it might be assumed that, although vocational teachers cannot be characterized as genetically talented in music or artistic term, they possessed personality traits of leaders, communicators or performers. These characteristics shaped and manifested in interactions to the playmates or domestic situations. The childhood environment of interviewees, with some exceptions, was modest in economic terms but had an educative role, as values like diligence, politeness were frequently formed in the childhood environment.

4.2 The aspects and outcomes of direct learning

Becoming a vocational teacher was unplanned and connected to structural factors (such as local labour market situation), additional benefits (the chance to get a free apartment), interest in teachers' profession, mission. Despite the reasons which lead to vocational teaching, interviewees brought out that they dared to accept vocational teachers work after comparing herself/himself to acquainted vocational teacher, considering their long work-experience and acquired skills and characteristics of personal traits. Thus, the decision to become a vocational teacher bases on previous informal and formal learning outcomes and perceived personal capacities, which in turn are related to internal reflection or external feedback, which are considered as a direct learning outcome. As becoming a vocational teacher mostly happened unexpectedly, the preparation period was rather short. At the beginning of the vocational teachers' career, the qualification of teachers varied a lot. Some had an academic education some had acquired vocation without a gymnasium education.

I told that I do not even have an education, only eight classes ... I was then 27, maybe around 28. And, and then I went to school just to try because this previous teacher had gone to the hospital with heart-attack because then they needed a teacher. And as I had so much experience working at building sites then I was a proper candidate, and it was enough in their eyes. (Ene, 64)

The interviewees brought out that before practising teachers work, they thought the job was easier. To manage a role, vocational teachers intuitively used experiences gained during their studies or raising their children. While working, they started continuous and purposeful learning (seeking the material, attended courses, academic education, collaboration with practitioners) to be competent to teach/in vocational pedagogy.

And then I came to this school as a teacher. In the beginning, I thought that I have a lot of experience in building – that, what there is to teach, but theory and all that... I had never studied building. Then I started to re-learn, I'm still learning, it's never-ending, it has been a non-stop studying to teach. (Arno, 58)

As vocational teachers did not have pedagogical qualification before starting as a teacher they were sent to pedagogical courses. Interviewees saw the courses differently. Some believed that pedagogical courses gave practical support. Some found that pedagogical courses were led by academics estranged from the reality of school life, and considered, therefore, courses useless. For example, Aivar, who considers the pedagogical courses at the University his worst experience, because he was taught by lecturers who have been in front of a class twenty-three years ago.

They had absolutely nothing to teach us. Nothing ... that's because time has moved on. (Aivar, 45)

Teachers' attitude to courses related to specific speciality was without exception positive. They found that these were useful for getting information related to occupational development or inevitable for maintaining qualification. Vocational teachers brought out that students' interest, their positive results and admiration are the best form of feedback. For some, preparing students for the skills competition was considered as a life goal.

I have only one dream and aim, that this same girl, with whom we trained for skills competition ... we are already so good that we got third place and our next aim is again next year, and then we will have the first place and then to the international skills competition... (Riina, 50)

Some compared their own time of study and found that they liked the way, how they themselves had learned. In this light, they were rather critical towards lecturers, whose theoretical advice according to changed teaching approach does not work in the real teaching situations.

Sometimes I have the feeling that those trainers haven't seen a 17-year-old who isn't interested in absolutely nothing. (Kairi, 45)

Most of the interviewees noted that they longed for a mentor who wasn't appointed for them. Several brought out that there was no support from the colleagues either. Some enjoyed the support of the mentor, which increased satisfaction with the school and made teachers adapt organisational norms and behaviours.

I was accepted quite well and I was appointed to an older colleague who was a very good person... He was like a tutor or a mentor...and I can say that all in all, it's a tradition to accept people very well in this school. (Tiia, 50)

In conclusion, acceptance of vocational teachers' work was related to self-understanding, which in turn was greatly a result of past learning experiences. The reality of vocational teachers' work turned out more difficult than expected. Only a few of the interviewed vocational teachers perceived mentor's or colleagues' support at the beginning. For managing difficulties, they used personal learning experiences and educational principles acquired in childhood. All of the vocational teachers had to pass through the pedagogical courses. Several did not consider courses efficient as these were led by theoreticians who did not know the school-life reality. Differently from traditional formal learning where students receive feedback from the teacher,

feedback to vocational teachers was given by students, colleagues, school leaders. Students' accomplishments at competitions, interest in the field, reactions in classes were the most explicit signs about vocational teachers' self-efficiency. In several cases, this was the only feedback for teachers in their learning journey as a vocational teacher.

4.3 Outcomes of indirect learning

Indirect learning explains how individual views on vocational education and vocational teaching change over time and analyses aspects according to which vocational teachers value vocational schools as a workplace and see their suitability for the profession. Interviewees who had learned in vocational schools themselves evaluated vocational schools' educational opportunities well. Those who had acquired an academic education noted that for them the vocational schools were rather unfamiliar or non-existent before starting the vocational teachers work.

Actually, when I was younger vocational education didn't even exist in my reality and well because I wasn't part of it, didn't know about it. So, I didn't even know what to think about it. (Tiia, 50)

During vocational teaching, people started to revalue learning opportunities given by vocational schools. All of the vocational teachers believed that their specific field is important for the student. Still, teachers found that the limitation of general subjects in learning programmes decreases vocational education's popularity among students as it is considered as "blind alley" compared by general secondary education. Some of the vocational teachers found that vocational education enables people to have a prosperous career.

The fact that there are qualifications and occupational standards in a specific field enables people to have a career in their occupational field. You acquire an occupation learn more, vocational schools give the chance to make a qualification exam. In addition to 'regular' diploma, you have a certificate in a specific field. I think it will become more and more valuable for the employer. (Rita, 56)

Several long-time vocational teachers thought that high school/general secondary education is overrated. They found that it is easier for teachers in high school because the majority of the students who continue studies in high school have better results and a more supportive background.

An ordinary gymnasium, that one is really a factory. Some faces come in, then they give a dose of each subject and maybe later a reject will go the street. ... Here comes the reject, mostly. Here we have to make reject into the material. (Aivar, 45)

In most cases, interviewees believed that the workplace environment is better in vocational schools than in high schools. Collegial relationships, together with speciality field mission turned to be the most important aspects of work motivation.

The motivator is the hugely cool bunch, with whom we work together because the salary is not as high, ... and another thing, you just have to be, I am a fanatic. (Riina, 50)

The decrease of workplace quality (e.g. unsupportive management) harmed work, private life, overall wellbeing, sleeping quality. Changes in the workplace environment, the arrogance of the school board members were the reasons for quitting vocational teachers work.

Two years I thought that there will be some changes and the director will find something in the end... Let's be honest – teacher's job is rather stressful and workplace environment has a huge impact. (Siiri, 53)

When it came to material infrastructure in vocational schools, teachers were on different opinions. In most cases, interviewees brought out that material resources (technology, equipment, buildings) were modern and of high quality. Some teachers found that technological appliances were out of date. Some vocational teachers consciously avoided traditional pedagogical principles. Here one of the reasons was the perception gained during their studies and related indirect learning, that life-long pedagogues have become distanced from real life and see the world through their specific field. For example, Mart's experience shows how significantly indirect learning connected to the professional group shape individual understanding and influence individual practice.

Maybe my advantage is that I haven't passed a teachers' training or something like that. /.../ The way how each teacher approaches a student is their own business. I don't interfere with that if there isn't an urgent need. At the same time, I also don't let other teachers ruin my class. (Mart, 33)

In conclusion, interviewees started to value the importance of vocational schools after becoming vocational teachers. Vocational teachers pointed out the practical value of vocational education. It was brought out that relationships between the colleagues and mission to share speciality filed skills are the most important motivators of work.

4.4 Task approach skills and subjective suitability for the profession

Vocational teachers related own suitability at the workplace with a former career, life experiences, self-efficacy, suitable personal characteristics. Several interviewees brought out that during their own student time or at work they were often chosen to be mentors or coaches for others student or co-workers.

A teacher chose me as a mentor for some students... There were so many of us in catering and the director sent me. I don't know whether he saw I had something in me, that something that I'll manage. (Siiri, 53)

Several vocational teachers perceived that the lack of technological skills hinders to complete duties as vocational teachers. Some of the middle-aged teachers (in the 50s and 60s) worried that due to their age they are no longer attractive as a teacher and at the labour market. They found that students need to see younger people as teachers.

I feel that there should be a younger person in front of the class. I am no longer an admirable candidate, at least in some places. (Rita, 56)

On the other hand, some teachers found that despite the changes in their physical capabilities they could still teach occupational offspring in educating the younger generation.

In sum, interviewees understanding of their suitability for vocational teachers' role bases on perceived self-efficacy related to task approach skills, which in turn are formed on interrelated aspects of environmental influences and the result of direct and indirect learning. As a result of direct learning, the individuals understand their capacities (innate teaching skills, speciality field know-how). At the same time, indirect learning plays a role. For example, vocational teachers' understanding of their suitability for the role is influenced by societal attitude (e.g. the cult of youth).

4.5 The importance of acquired skills for future career

Interviewees noted that the teacher's profession has enabled them to complement their practical skills, handle new technology etc. They believed that due to vocational teaching, they had received more professional courses and training than they would have while working in the private sector.

Most of the interviewees brought out that due to vocational teaching they are better communicators, collaborators, motivators, team-players. Teachers also noted creativity, flexibility and critical thinking. Some of these qualities were noticed also by two former vocational teachers. They found that they can utilize previously acquired skills at their present work.

Now that teacher's job and pedagogical courses, it has helped how to speak and communicate with people. To be honest, it also learnt how to influence people. (Siri, 53)

Teachers recognised the importance of courses, but the prevailing part of skills was an outcome of informal learning which in turn is the result of everyday experiences, judgements, intuitive problem-solving. Courses are related to practical or occupational and pedagogical skills and know-how; everyday actions facilitate so-called soft-skills development. Aforementioned skills are performance indicators, but at the same time, these skills are valued by employers in the labour markets.

5 Discussion

The study highlights the outcomes of direct and indirect learning, which are related to life-long experiences within particular environmental conditions. Although learning results may reveal retrospectively, they play the role of sense-making of one's professional capacity and career decision making.

As learning is a life-long process, we have to recognize the influence of genetic endowment and a childhood environment. Vocational teachers cannot be characterized as genetically talented. One reason here might be childhood environment as the family could not offer proper support to develop the specific talents. A large group of interviewees grew up with foster parents or with grandparents, where they had to do a lot of practical work. Interviewees' first career choice was influenced by a socioeconomic situation or parent's occupation. In this, individual educational decision making was dependent on external factors, which according to Krumboltz et al. (1976) is usually outside the control of an individual. However, the childhood environment paved the way for preferences, values, and working habits.

Although interviewees did not choose teaching as their first career path, they often received the role of a mentor in work or during studies. The mentor role proved to be a direct learning experience, which encouraged individuals to believe in their teaching skills. However, pedagogical qualification was acquired after becoming a vocational teacher. Teachers' attitude towards pedagogical courses was dependent on their practical usefulness for teaching work. In their work, vocational teachers used teaching skills they had acquired from multiple sources during their studies, through parenting, work experiences, reading psychological books, through formal learning.

Becoming a vocational teacher brought about the re-evaluation of views about the reputation of vocational education. Vocational teachers started to evaluate vocational education more than a high-school education and the vocational teachers' work was considered more meaningful than teachers' work in a high school. The differentiation of „we“ and „they“ indicates to the developments of the workplace or occupational identity. Here the results of our study are in harmony with Beckett and Hager (2002) explanation that workplaces as social context shape individual as far "they are becoming a certain sort of individual" (p, 27). More precisely, they

become professionals with vocational and teacher identity, who tend to value practical knowledge and have a feeling of a mission to share these skills. In order to realize their professional potential, they need a supportive work environment and a sense of belonging related to the quality of collegial relations. The deterioration of workplace relation proved to be the reason for quitting the profession.

Our study highlighted the multidimensional development and learning of vocational teachers. Vocational teachers' profession stimulated individuals to complement knowledge in their speciality field, made them better team-players, enriched critical thinking, creativity. Thus, complementary to speciality field and pedagogical skills, soft-skills or transferable skills improved. Personal development, positive feedback, workplace relations, the chance to see students' development made vocational teaching personally meaningful, increased the feeling of stability, encouraged to continue in the field.

Our findings confirm the very social nature of learning of vocational teachers. Individual learning experiences throughout the lifespan may be direct or indirect. However, the associated feedback or interpretation influences individual self-understanding and suitability for a certain career.

The study points out that an individual considers becoming a vocational teacher once a person sees oneself as a specialist and he/she perceives to have personal traits suitable for a teacher. Becoming a vocational teacher broadens the studying opportunities, diversifies the know-how and therefore, boosts personal development and satisfaction as well as perspectives at the labour market.

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